

Synthesis of sphingosine relatives. Part-26^Ψ : Synthesis of ceramide 1 {(2*S*, 3*R*, 4*E*)-*N*-[30'-(linoleoyloxy)triacontanoyl]-4-sphingenine}, a unique constituent of human skin[†]

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Ceramide 1 {(2*S*,3*R*,4*E*)-*N*-[30'-(linoleoyloxy)triacontanoyl]-4-sphingenine, **1**}, a unique ceramide of human epidermal stratum corneum, was synthesized from (*S*)-Garner's aldehyde (**2**), pentadecan-15-olide (**5**) and linoleic acid.

Lipids containing linoleic acid are essential compounds in the maintenance of the epidermal water barrier of human skin, which protects the human body from loss of water^{1,2}. Ceramides constitute the major solvent-extractable lipids of human epidermal stratum corneum³. Ceramide 1 (**1**, Fig 1) comprises 8% of the free and extractable ceramides of human epidermis, and contains linoleic acid. So far, no synthesis of **1** has been reported, although Mori and Matsuda synthesized an epidermal cerebroside with a similar linoleic ester structure as early as in 1991⁴.

Because ceramides are important for skin function, they themselves or their relatives and mimics are used in cosmetic industry as skin-care creams and lotions. However, ceramides

seem to be related to cell apoptosis^{5,6}, and it is necessary to precisely examine the cell biology associated with ceramides. In this context, we have started our work to synthesize ceramide 1 (**1**) so as to examine whether it induces apoptosis or not. This paper reports the successful synthesis of **1**.

As shown in Fig. 1, ceramide 1 (**1**) can be dissected into three building blocks, **A**, **B** and **C**. Linoleic acid (**C**) is commercially available, while sphingosine (**A**) and 30-hydroxytriacontanoic acid (**B**) must be synthesized.

Fig. 2 summarizes our synthesis of ceramide 1 (**1**). Garner's aldehyde **2** is a well-established starting material for sphingosine synthesis⁷⁻⁹. Treatment of **2** with lithium pentadecynide gave **3**, which was reduced with lithium in

Fig. 1. Structure of ceramide 1 and its retrosynthetic analysis.

^ΨPart-25 : M. Ichihashi and K. Mori, *Biosci. Biotechnol. Biochem.*, 2003, **67**, 329.

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Fig. 2. Synthesis of ceramide 1 (**1**). Reagents : (a) $\text{Me}(\text{CH}_2)_{12}\text{C}\equiv\text{CH}$, *n*-BuLi, THF (71%); (b) Li, EtNH₂, THF; (c) TBSOTf, 2,6-lutidine, CH_2Cl_2 (88%, 2 steps); (d) $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$, CH_2Cl_2 (93%); (e) **4**, $\text{C}_5\text{H}_5\text{N}$ (70%); (f) TBAF, THF (82%).

ethylamine to give sphingosine through concomitant removal of the protective group. The two hydroxy groups of sphingosine were protected as *tert*-butyldimethylsilyl (TBS) ethers to give **4** in 62% overall yield based on **2** (3 steps). For the construction of the side-chain part of **1**, commercially available pentadecan-15-olide (**5**) was converted to *p*-nitrophenyl 30-hydroxytriacontanoate (**6**) by the reported procedure⁴. Acylation of **6** with linoleoyl chloride (**7**) gave the known activated ester **8**. The protected sphingosine **4** was then treated with **8** in the presence of pyridine to give bis-TBS-protected ceramide **1** (**9**). Finally the TBS protective groups of **9** were removed by treatment with tetra(*n*-butyl)ammonium fluoride (TBAF) in THF to give ceramide **1** (**1**) as an amorphous solid. Its 500 MHz ¹H NMR spectrum was in good agreement with the structure **1**.

In conclusion, we synthesized ceramide **1** (**1**) in 35% overall yield (5 steps) based on Garner's aldehyde (**2**) or 29% overall yield (12 steps) based on pentadecan-15-olide (**5**). The biological properties of **1** is now under investigation, and will be published in due course.

Experimental

Melting point (m.p.) data were measured with a Yanaco MP-S3 instrument and are uncorrected. IR spectra were mea-

sured with a Jasco FT/IR-460 spectrometer. ¹H NMR spectra were recorded at 90 MHz by a Jeol JNM-EX 90A spectrometer, at 400 MHz by a Jeol JNM-LA400 spectrometer, and at 500 MHz by a Jeol JNM-LA500 spectrometer. The peak for TMS, or CHCl_3 in CDCl_3 (at δ 7.26), was used as the internal standard. ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded at 100 MHz by a Jeol JNM-LA400 spectrometer and at 126 MHz by a Jeol JNM-LA500 spectrometer. The peak for CDCl_3 (at δ 77.0) was used as the internal standard. Optical rotation values were measured with a Jasco P-1010 polarimeter, and mass spectra were measured with a Jeol JMS-SX102A spectrometer. Column chromatography was carried out on Merck Kieselgel 60 Art 1.07734, and TLC analyses were performed on Merck 60F-254 silica gel plates.

tert-Butyl (4*S*,1'*R*)-4-(1'-hydroxy-2'-hexadecynyl)-2,2-dimethyl-3-oxazolidinecarboxylate (**3**): To a stirred solution of 1-pentadecyne (17.92 g, 86.1 mmol) in dry THF (600 ml) was added *n*-butyllithium (1.59 M in hexane; 54.1 ml, 86.1 mmol) dropwise at -40° under Ar. After the reaction mixture had been stirred at -23° for 1.5 h, a solution of Garner's aldehyde (**2**, 23.7 g, 103.3 mmol) in dry THF (160 ml) was added dropwise at -40° . After having been stirred at -23° for 1.5 h, the resulting solution was quenched with water and extracted with ethyl acetate. The extract was successively washed with water and brine, dried with MgSO_4 , and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was chromatographed on silica gel to give **3** (26.72 g, 71%) as a colorless oil n_D^{23} 1.4607. $[\alpha]_D^{25}$ -44.9 (*c* 1.00, CHCl_3); IR ν_{max} (film) cm^{-1} 3460 (br.w, OH), 2230 (w, $\text{C}\equiv\text{C}$), 1705 (s, $\text{C}=\text{O}$); NMR δ_{H} (400 MHz, CDCl_3) 0.88 (3H, t, *J* 6.7 Hz, 16'-H), 1.23–1.37 (15H, m, *t*-Bu, 2-Me, 2-Me), 1.45–1.67 (23H, m, 5'–15'-H₂, 1'-OH), 2.19 (2H, dt, *J* 7.1, 1.7 Hz, 4'-H₂), 3.91 (1H, br.s, 1'-H), 4.00–4.12 (2H, m, 3-H₂), 4.49 (1H, br.s, 4-H) (Found : C, 71.57; H, 10.76; N, 3.11. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{26}\text{H}_{47}\text{NO}_4$: C, 71.35; H, 10.82; N, 3.20%).

(2*S*,3*R*,4*E*)-2-Amino-1,3-bis-*tert*-butyldimethylsilyloxy-4-octadecene (**4**): A solution of **3** (5.74 g, 13.12 mmol) in dry THF (50 ml) was added dropwise to a blue solution of lithium (2.66 g, 394 mmol) in ethylamine (41 g) while stirring at -78° for 1 h. The mixture was then stirred overnight while being allowed to warm to room temperature, before being quenched with NH_4Cl (*ca.* 43 g, 785 mmol). After removing the ethylamine by evaporation, the mixture was diluted with water and extracted with diethyl ether. The extract was successively washed with water and brine, dried with Na_2SO_4 , and concentrated under reduced pressure to give the reduction product (4.25 g) as a brown waxy solid. This reduction product was used for the next reaction without purification.

To a stirred solution of the reduction product (4.25 g) in dry CH_2Cl_2 (70 ml) were added 2,6-dimethylpyridine (2,6-dimethylpyridine; 7.7 ml, 66.5 mmol) and TBSOTf (12.0 ml, 53.2 mmol) at 0° . After having been stirred at room temperature for 1 h, the resulting solution was quenched with methanol. It was then poured into water and extracted with diethyl ether. The extract was successively washed with water, saturated aq. NaHCO_3 and brine, dried with MgSO_4 , and concentrated under reduced pressure. The residue was chromatographed on silica gel to give **4** (5.88 g, 2 steps, 88%) as a pale yellow oil, n_D^{22} 1.4556. $[\alpha]_D^{26}$ -1.18 (c 1.00, CHCl_3); IR ν_{max} (film) cm^{-1} 1255 (s, Si-Me), 1090 (s, O-Si-O); NMR δ_{H} (400 MHz, CDCl_3) 0.01, 0.04 (6H, each s, Si-Me), 0.05 (6H, s, Si-Me), 0.85–0.90 (21H, m, *t*-Bu, 18- H_3), 1.22–1.38 (22H, m, 7–17 H_2), 1.45–1.53 (2H, br.s, N- H_2), 2.03 (2H, dd, J 13.4, 6.8 Hz, 6- H_2), 2.74 (1H, dt, J 6.7, 4.7 Hz, 2-H), 3.53 (1H, dd, J 9.6, 6.7 Hz, 1- H_a), 3.68 (1H, dd, J 9.6, 4.7 Hz, 1- H_b), 4.00 (1H, t, J 6.7 Hz, 3-H), 5.37 (1H, dd, J 15.4, 6.7 Hz, 4-H), 5.60 (1H, dt, J 15.4, 6.8 Hz, 5-H) (Found : C, 68.06; H, 12.67; N, 2.67. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{30}\text{H}_{65}\text{NO}_2\text{Si}_2$: C, 68.24; H, 12.41; N, 2.65%).

(2*S*,3*R*,4*E*)-*N*-[30'-(Linoleoyloxy)triacontanoyl]-1,3-*O*-(bis-*tert*-butyldimethylsilyl)-4-sphingenine (**9**) : A solution of **4** (100 mg, 0.19 mmol) and **8** (168 mg, 0.23 mmol) in pyridine (5 ml) was stirred at 45° for 24 h. The mixture was diluted with benzene (50 ml) and concentrated under reduced pressure. This operation was repeated three times to remove pyridine. The residue was chromatographed on silica gel to give **9** (164 mg, 70%) as a colorless oil, n_D^{26} 1.4729. $[\alpha]_D^{26}$ -0.8 (c 1.05, CHCl_3); IR ν_{max} (film) cm^{-1} 3315 (w, NH), 1740 (in, C=O), 1650 (w, CON), 1255 (m, Si-Me), 1085 (m, O-Si-O); NMR δ_{H} (500 MHz, CDCl_3) 0.003, 0.026, 0.043, 0.050 (12H, each s, Si-Me), 0.87–0.90 (24H, m, *t*-Bu, 18-, 18''- H_3), 1.25–1.39 (92H, m, 7–17- H_2 , 3'~29'- H_2 , 3''~7''- H_2 , 15''~17''- H_2), 1.97–2.17 (8H, m, 6-, 2', 8', 14''- H_2), 2.29 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, 2'- H_2), 2.77 (1H, t-like, J 6.2 Hz, 11''- H_2), 3.58 (1H, dd, J 10.0, 5.0 Hz, 1- H_a), 3.84 (1H, dd, J 10.0, 4.0 Hz, 1- H_b), 4.05 (2H, t-like, J 6.8 Hz, 3-H), 4.19 (1H, t-like, J 6.8 Hz, 3-H), 5.30–5.42 (4H, m, 9''-, 10''-, 12''- 13''-H), 5.44 (1H, d, J 7.0 Hz, N-H), 5.52–5.61 (2H, m, 4-, 5-H) (Found : C, 75.37; H, 12.63; N, 1.34. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{78}\text{H}_{153}\text{NO}_5\text{Si}_2$: C, 75.48; H, 12.42; N, 1.13%).

(2*S*,3*R*,4*E*)-*N*-[30'-(Linoleoyloxy)triacontanoyl]-4-sphingenine (**1**) : To a stirred mixture of **9** (80 mg, 0.064 mmol) in dry THF (5 ml) was added TBAF in THF (1.0 M, 0.19 ml, 0.19 mmol) at 0° under Ar, and stirring was

continued for 4 h at room temperature. The mixture was then diluted with chloroform (10 ml) and concentrated under reduced pressure. This operation was repeated three times to remove THF. The residue was chromatographed on silica gel to give **1** (53 mg, 82%) as an amorphous solid, m.p. 86.0 – 88.0° . $[\alpha]_D^{22}$ -1.67 (c 1.40, CHCl_3); IR ν_{max} (film) cm^{-1} 3305 (br.s, OH), 1735 (s, C=O), 1645 (w, CON), 1550 (s, NH), 1100 (m, C-O); NMR δ_{H} (500 MHz, CDCl_3) : 0.86–0.90 (6H, m, 18-, 18''- H_3), 1.20–1.38 (94H, m, 7–17- H_2 , 3'~29'- H_2 , 3''~7''- H_2 , 15''~17''- H_2 , OH), 2.01–2.08 (6H, m, 6-, 8', 14''- H_2), 2.22 (2H, t, J 7.5 Hz, 2'- H_2), 2.77 (1H, t-like, J 6.8 Hz, 11''- H_2), 3.65–3.73 (1H, m, 2-H), 3.87–3.93 (1H, m, 1- H_a), 3.94–3.98 (1H, m, 1- H_b), 4.05 (2H, t-like, J 6.8 Hz, 30'-H), 4.28–4.43 (1H, m, 3-H), 5.28–5.40 (4H, m, 9''-, 10''-, 12''-, 13''-H), 5.53 (1H, dd, J 15.5, 6.5 Hz, 4-H), 5.78 (1H, dt, J 15.5, 6.8 Hz, 5-H), 6.23 (1H, d, J 7.5 Hz, N-H); NMR δ_{C} (126 MHz, CDCl_3) 14.05, 14.10, 22.55, 22.67, 24.99, 25.59, 25.74, 25.91, 28.62, 29.10, 29.15, 29.21, 29.24, 29.28, 29.32, 29.34, 29.36, 29.48, 29.51, 29.57, 29.61, 29.64, 29.69, 31.50, 31.90, 32.27, 34.38, 36.82, 54.47, 62.45, 64.42, 74.56, 127.87, 128.00, 128.77, 130.01, 130.18, 134.20, 173.94, 174.02 (Found : C, 78.12; H, 12.52; N, 1.31. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{66}\text{H}_{125}\text{NO}_5$: C, 78.28; H, 12.44; N, 1.38%).

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